

STEM-EF qualitative analysis in the second iteration

Next you will judge items associated with the Sprint Planning ceremony.

When refining the Product Backlog, my team...

considers the emotional needs of less experienced members, estimating and prioritizing tasks collaboratively. [01-IE-Attention]

Expert 4

When people feel motivated, respected and safe, they tend to participate more in the refinement, contributing to the quality of decisions.

Expert 7

demonstrates attention to the emotional needs of less experienced members by collectively estimating and prioritizing tasks.

Expert 1

Less experienced members need to be invited to participate. Furthermore, some studies define how WOMEN suffer some kind of repression simply because they are women. For example, their suggestions require further validation or are disregarded. Look for the concept of COMMUNITY SMELLS (SEE ARTICLE Gender Diversity and Community Smells: A Double-Replication Study on Brazilian Software Teams).

Expert 5

I don't think it's necessary to justify this, because it's clear to me that this point is relevant. Newcomers should be given every attention they need to generate positive feelings that motivate them and foster a sense of belonging.

Expert 6

I believe the content of the item is relevant, however, often team members will be so focused on refinement that it will be difficult to care about the emotional needs of less experienced members.

When refining the Product Backlog, my team...

demonstrates ability to negotiate priorities with the Product Owner (P.O), seeking to balance their needs with the team's capacity.[02-HI-Negotiation]

Expert 1

Situations that may arise in practice: A PO who isn't a programming expert may have difficulty translating their definitions into a programming project, potentially leading to difficulties in understanding and negotiation (prioritization, for example). The PO may hold an administrative position, so their hierarchy may be higher than that of the rest of the team, compromising the validity of SCRUM. Therefore, negotiating with a PO involves the PO first and foremost understanding their role within the team.

Expert 5

It's important to be able to negotiate priorities while balancing team capacity, as demands that exceed the team's capabilities or misleading estimates are common. This generates anxiety and other social issues within the team, in addition to affecting productivity.

Expert 6

The item is quite relevant to avoid incorrect predictions of demand deliveries.

Already defining the Sprint Goal, my team...

clearly understands emotions by noticing signs of confusion or hesitation from the P.O. or other team members in discussions about the Sprint Goal. [03-IE-Clarity]

Expert 4

The same emotional factors I mentioned for Refinement apply here, and I'd add, in particular, the "safety to take risks." If the team feels confident in trying difficult things, they'll set more ambitious Sprint Goals with greater potential to generate value; however, if a manager is annoying them with bureaucratic tasks like demanding hours and punishing failures, the team will always be left with nothing but bread and butter.

Expert 1

EMOTIONS ARE NOT ALWAYS SHOWN WHEN MAKING THIS DECISION, SO IT IS WORTH ASKING THIS QUESTION.

Expert 5

I think it's important for the team to clearly understand the sprint objective, not just from the task descriptions, but also from the PO's perspective. It's common for tasks to be unclear.

Expert 6

It's important to understand the stress level of the PO and the team, as in a less stressful environment, all members feel more comfortable and less pressured to deliver results.

Already defining the Sprint Goal, my team...

feel safe discussing technical challenges without assigning blame [04-SP-Non-Guilt]

Expert 6

I believe guilt is generated, especially if mistakes were made during a Sprint. If it's the first Sprint, I believe this feeling of guilt won't exist.

In adjusting the Sprint plan, my team...

demonstrates ability to deal with negative emotions caused by sudden changes in scope, ensuring that the Sprint Goal remains realistic and achievable [05-IE-Repair]

Expert 4

I liked this one. I've worked with people who were very frustrated with scope changes, but sometimes it's inevitable and you have to know how to deal with it.

Expert 5

Emotional control is crucial when plans change during the sprint. Complaints and team burnout are common due to these changes.

Expert 6

Sudden changes in scope are challenging, making it important to define strategies for reallocating activities to minimize delays.

In adjusting the Sprint plan, my team...

makes a collective decision about the Sprint Backlog [06-SP-Collective Decision Making]

Expert 5

This is linked to the team's proactivity and self-management. It's crucial for the team to be cohesive to facilitate decision-making.

Expert 6

It's important to measure this item, but developers often don't have much say in certain decisions about the Sprint Backlog. For example, which tasks should be completed first will depend primarily on the PO.

In the effort estimate, my team...

demonstrates maturity in dealing with disagreements, ensuring that different opinions are respected and considered, with the aim of ensuring balanced and inclusive planning for the Sprint [07-RC-Maturity]

Expert 4

wow... I've seen a lot of problems here, you know... every now and then there's someone who thinks they're right and wants to dominate

Expert 5

I think this point is related to the first question. This is very common when dealing with newcomers. It takes a certain level of team maturity to align expectations and task estimates.

Expert 6

Estimating the effort required for tasks is a highly complex activity that naturally generates friction. For example, one developer might estimate an activity as having a complexity level of 3, while another with more experience might estimate the complexity level as 1.

In the effort estimate, my team...

demonstrates the ability to communicate assertively, ensuring that all points of view are considered and understood [08-HI-Communication]

Expert 6

I believe there's an effort to ensure the team understands each other overall, but sometimes information gets lost. That's why it's important for the Scrum Master and PO to communicate with the developers to ensure their needs are being met as expected.

Next you will judge items associated with the Daily Scrum ceremony

When identifying impediments, my team...

demonstrates attention to the emotions of members in situations of dissatisfaction in the distribution of tasks, ensuring a more balanced distribution [09-IE-Attention]

Expert 4

Although I don't really like the concept of "balanced distribution of tasks," because I'm not sure what you mean by it, I marked it as relevant because the ideal here is for everyone to choose their tasks, but the decision should be focused on the Sprint Goal and the team should be in agreement. If this isn't being followed (e.g., the Scrum Master allocating activities to people), I assume there's an "imbalance" occurring and that would generate dissatisfaction.

Expert 6

I believe that, in practice, effort is measured based on the team's average effort and team experience. For example, a more experienced developer performing less complex tasks will score a 1, but if they notice that other less experienced developers on the team are scoring 3 for tasks of the same complexity, they will naturally increase their score. This can generate dissatisfaction and necessitate adjustments in scoring within the team.

When identifying impediments, my team...

demonstrates ability to negotiate the redistribution of tasks in a collaborative and transparent manner, adjusting the workload based on the progress of members [10-HI-Negotiation]

When identifying impediments, my team...

demonstrates maturity by deal with discontent, ensuring that differences are resolved constructively [11-RC-Maturity]

Expert 6

It depends a lot on the maturity of the team, but often differences cannot be resolved constructively, but the work needs to continue despite the differences.

When identifying impediments, my team...

demonstrates skill in manage negative emotions associated with the inability to deliver what was agreed to the customer, providing transparent information. [12-IE-Repair]

Expert 6

Typically, the PO can identify which developers are more skilled. For example, while one developer takes 1 day to complete a specific task, another may take 5. The ability to manage negative emotions improves as results are delivered. Otherwise, disagreements and arguments tend to increase.

When identifying impediments, my team...

demonstrates the ability to communicate assertively, allowing the day's priorities to be adjusted while maintaining focus on the Sprint objective [13-HI-Communication]

Expert 5

This item is very important and can certainly measure interpersonal communication skills.

In reviewing daily commitments, my team...

clearly expresses emotional concerns, ensuring everyone is aligned and comfortable with the workload [14-IE-Clarity]

In reviewing daily commitments, my team...

demonstrates collaboration in distributing Sprint Backlog items, ensuring that all team members maintain a balance of responsibilities. [15-RC-Collaboration]

Expert 6

I believe it's very difficult to maintain a balance of activities. Most of the time, some developers will work more or at least be able to deliver more tasks in less time.

In reviewing daily commitments, my team...

avoids blaming members when identifying impediments [16-SP-Non-Guilt]

Expert 6

It's an important item, but when deadlines start to get tight, the team will usually point fingers and place blame on whoever was actually late or took too long to deliver the demand.

Next you will judge items associated with the Sprint Review ceremony.

In analyzing the Sprint results, my team...

demonstrates ability to manage negative emotions after feedback from the P.O, transforming difficulties into learning opportunities for the next Sprint. [17-IE-Repair]

Expert 6

I believe that only negative emotions will be generated if the sprint doesn't meet its objective. If the sprint didn't meet its objective, some demands can be shifted to the next sprint without major problems. I imagine the problem will be greater the more frequent the delays and the lack of understanding of the requirements.

In analyzing the Sprint results, my team...

demonstrates ability to negotiate changes after feedback from the P.O. and stakeholders, ensuring that the changes fit the team's capabilities. [18-HI-Negotiation]

Expert 6

I believe that negotiating changes is directly related to the deadline for the request. For example, if there's a new feature that needs to be developed by a specific date, as determined by the National Council of Justice (CNJ), and that date clearly won't be met, this will naturally put the team and, consequently, the PO under greater stress. However, if the request is more flexible and allows for delays, negotiation will be easier.

In analyzing the Sprint results, my team...

demonstrates the ability to communicate assertively when presenting software increments, ensuring that stakeholders understand the results achieved as well as the next steps of the project [19-HI-Communication]

Expert 1

The team isn't always able to demonstrate in a way that the customer truly understands. Often, the stakeholder isn't even available for discussion during increment launches or at the end of the sprint. This difficulty needs to be mitigated, and planning is crucial for communication skills and the ability to synchronize the participation of all stakeholders.

Expert 6

The question is important, and the team's communication skills are crucial. Poor communication often leads to the development of features that aren't exactly what stakeholders wanted. Furthermore, communication with stakeholders typically only occurs at the end of feature development, that is, after every sprint.

In the software increment demo, my team...

clearly expresses the emotions associated with the results achieved, ensuring that all stakeholders understand the impact of the deliverables on the project's progress
[20-IE-Clarity]

Expert 1

There's rarely any such explanation about emotions. The focus is more on the discussion of development.

In the software increment demo, my team...

demonstrates ability to deal with negative emotions when receiving feedback from stakeholders [21-IE-Repair]

Expert 1

The focus is simply on accepting feedback. No matter how negative the feedback, the team will focus on doing what was asked, without further discussion, even if they're upset.

Expert 6

In some cases, it's easier to deal with stakeholders than with the team itself. This is because stakeholders typically don't have the technical expertise to know how long it will take to develop a new feature, but they will want to know a deadline. Typically, developers will already commit to this deadline with the PO. In other words, delays for stakeholders will have a domino effect on the team's stress, meaning the PO will become more stressed, and this stress will be 'transferred' down the chain until the issues are resolved and the demand is met.

In the software increment demo, my team...

demonstrates ability to transform critical feedback into growth opportunities
[22-IE-Repair]

Expert 1

This type of Emotional Intelligence is not common.

Expert 6

I believe the team will acquire this skill over time and with experience. Furthermore, it relies heavily on critical feedback; if it's fair, it's easier to turn it into a growth opportunity. However, if there are unfair complaints, people may take it personally, which can end up damaging team relationships. There have been cases where changes clearly needed to be made within development teams because the PO or Scrum Master realized that some people weren't as productive working together.

Next you will judge items associated with the Sprint Retrospective ceremony

In reflecting on team performance, my team...

demonstrates attention to members' emotions, ensuring that everyone feels comfortable and motivated [23-IE-Attention]

Expert 1

It is more common to have discussions to motivate

Expert 6

I believe it's not so easy to pay attention to members' emotions while the team is focused on reflecting on team performance and whether the Sprint goal was achieved. However, if a member is clearly tired or emotionally distressed, some support will be provided.

In reflecting on team performance, my team...

feel comfortable reflecting on failures without fear of judgment or criticism [24-SP-Non-Guilt]

Expert 1

It's not common, people generally don't respond to comments from superiors. They just gossip, lol.

Expert 6

I believe this reflection on failures is easy if the error was minor, but when serious failures occur, it's difficult not to fear judgment. However, depending on the team's maturity, people will be able to admit when they've made mistakes and how they can correct them and provide solutions.

In the lessons learned discussion, my team...

demonstrates ability to communicate openly and honestly about improvements, ensuring that all opinions are considered [25-HI-Communication]

Expert 1

To discuss improvements, people are more open to communication and negotiation to actually change/improve

Expert 6

Yes, my team typically listens to a wide range of opinions and approaches to problem-solving or improvement. However, there are always people who are more verbose and end up talking too much. So, sometimes it's necessary to balance what you say to prioritize the most important things.

In the lessons learned discussion, my team...

demonstrates collaboration among team members to effectively manage conflict
[26-RC-Collaboration]

Expert 6

Yes, a relevant item for measuring dimensionality. Collaboration is crucial. For example, let's say a PO was working on a request and went on vacation. Someone else needs to take over the request to meet deadlines. In other words, the team must be collaborative.

In the lessons learned discussion, my team...

demonstrates maturity when discussing conflicts, with the aim of strengthening team relationships and promoting continuous improvements [27-RC-Maturity]

In planning changes for the next Sprint, my team...

Demonstrates ability to negotiate process improvements and changes with the team and stakeholders for the next Sprint, ensuring that all parties agree to the proposed adjustments. [28-HI-Negotiation]

Expert 1

Negotiating with people outside the team requires skills in dealing with various different types of people. A team member who is primarily a developer will likely not be able to perform this task well. It's expected that the person performing this task has been trained or possesses these negotiation skills to ensure that this activity doesn't have negative impacts on the project (such as unexpected changes, underestimation of deadlines and tasks, or delays).

Expert 6

Yes, but sometimes there's little room for negotiation. In other words, the final word will be, "We need to finish on time." So, the entire team will need to work harder than usual to meet the agreed

deadlines. If the time allotted was truly short, the deadline extension will usually be justified by some change or adjustment to the requirement.

In planning changes for the next Sprint, my team...

clearly expresses emotions when discussing what worked well and what can be improved [29-IE-Clarity]

Expert 1

This practice is quite common and usually does not present problems.

Expert 6

Relevant point. Processes are typically improved as failures occur. For example, initially at the AM Court of Justice, demands came from judges and appellate judges, who are the interested parties. However, these demands weren't formalized in the SEI system. That is, the judge would tell someone that they needed the system to do a certain thing. This person would then forward it to the IT department, and a PO would be assigned to that demand. However, the understanding of the person who received the information from the judge and passed it on to the IT team was one thing; the IT team might have interpreted the change differently, which ultimately led to incorrect requirements and incorrect features. Therefore, it became necessary to create requirements documents via SEI to formalize and document that the joint understanding was correct.

In planning changes for the next Sprint, my team...

makes decisions collectively in defining improvements and corrective actions
[30-SP-Collective Decision Making]

Expert 6

Most of the time, yes, however, there are times when it is not possible to allow too much interference from the collective, as the demand needs to be met.